

Human Security; Assessment of the Coping Mechanisms of Women and Children in IDPs Camps in Abuja, Nigeria

*Adah, Obaa Daniel, ¹Badey Dinebari

*Centre for Gender and Development Studies, University of Port Harcourt

¹Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Port Harcourt.

Abstract

The present study is focused on assessing the coping mechanisms of women and children in IDPs camps in Abuja as components of the Human security needs of these vulnerable groups of persons. The theoretical background was the Human Needs theory. The study employed a survey research design using mixed method for data collection, quantitative data was obtained by the administration of questionnaires while qualitative data was gotten through key informant interview schedule, participants were drawn using purposive sampling technique. The data generated using the questionnaires was analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages, presented in tables. The data generated from the interview schedule was analyzed using the explanation building technique. The results showed that women and children had applied coping mechanisms to address the challenges faced in the IDP camps and these mechanisms have contributed to their overall human security, however, there is a mixed perception of the effectiveness of the interventions applied as there is need for more tailored, sustainable, and inclusive interventions. The study recommends amongst others collaboration and coordination among humanitarian actors, government agencies, local authorities, and community-based organizations to ensure a coherent and integrated response to the needs of displaced women and children, empowerment of women and youth as agents of change within the IDP camps by providing opportunities for leadership, skills development, and civic engagement.

Keywords: Internally Displaced Persons, Coping Mechanisms, interventions, Women and Children.

1.0 Introduction

Like many other African nations, Nigeria is strikingly incapable of offering human security that meets international standards. Nigeria has around one-third of Africa's IDP population and approximately 10% of the world's IDP population. Nigeria ranks third in the global ranking, with around 3.3 million displaced persons, primarily women and children (IDMC, 2018). Insecurity caused by the Boko Haram (BH) insurgency and military counter-insurgency operations affects around 26 million people in Northeast Nigeria, with over 14 million in desperate need of humanitarian assistance (OCHA, 2017). Women and children are typically

more vulnerable than other affected displaced populations, contributing to the grave human rights violations that they face (Brookings Institution, 2014).

Furthermore, women and children experience displacement in ways that men do not, and they face unique obstacles that must be acknowledged in order to offer them the proper and specific help they require (IDMC, 2020). Unfortunately, this distinction is rarely considered while giving aid and protection. Instead, gendered behaviors in IDP camps have reinforced previously existent discrimination against women and children. These IDP experiences, according to UNFPA (2016), are rooted in uneven and discriminatory social norms, gender inequity, and stereotypes. According to IDMC (2014), the ongoing lack of disaggregated data on displacement dynamics has resulted in a lack of awareness of Nigeria's displacement dynamics and fragmented, unsuitable, and ineffective response actions. As a result, internally displaced persons face many obstacles in various camps across Nigeria.

Nigeria has faced numerous hurdles since gaining its independence, including nation-building, industrial and scientific advances, political and economic development, high education standards, and health care quality. Human security has been a big concern for the Nigerian government despite the country's abundance of riches. It has also significantly weakened the country's economy by depressing investment and tourism. Many other elements work together to impede the attainment of human security, aside from the government's apathetic attitude towards it. Even worse, Nigeria is one of the nations where the most horrible terrorist organizations, like Boko Haram, are based, drawing attention, support, and engagement from around the world. Human insecurity has a detrimental impact on a country's ability to achieve the current Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and the upcoming Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Displaced persons are now more vulnerable as a result of internal displacement. In addition, it makes the victims' poverty worse, endangers national security, causes property loss and suffering, violates human rights, discriminates, malnourishes displaced children, and spreads diseases. Rape, child labor, poor health, and inadequate education have all claimed the lives of women and children. Notably, women, the victims of displacement, lack enough necessities (Walsh, 2016). Despite these concerns and issues, there is a distinct shortage of research evidence on human security in general, especially those facets of human security related to the sustenance of IDPs, such as food and social security. Most studies on IDPs have either focused on non-conflict-induced Displacement (non-CID) or, when focused on CID, have generally focused on reasons for displacement, types of displacement, and international legal instruments that control IDPs (Mehari, 2017). According to Taylor-Robinson and Oleribe (2016) and Bamidele (2023), most studies have not assessed the coping mechanisms of IDPs, especially women and children. IDPs in Nigeria are in a severe and precarious situation, with ever-worsening living conditions, including food and social insecurity. This should be considered in addition to the high frequency of human insecurity and IDPs' lack of a long-term solution (IDMC, 2019). As a result, this study seeks to assess the coping mechanisms of IDPs and the situation of women and children in the New Kuchingoro and Wassa Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) Camps as a means of offering suggestions and insights that can help find long-term solutions that will safeguard their human security.

Received: 22 August 2024

Revised: 2 September 2024

Accepted: 14 September 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13763596](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13763596)

1.1 Objectives of the Study

1. Determine the coping mechanisms employed by women and children in selected IDP Camps to address the challenges they face and their impact on their resilience and overall human security.
2. Evaluate the effectiveness of the coping mechanism employed by women and children in the selected IDP Camps in promoting human security.
3. Assess the effectiveness of the interventions implemented by different stakeholders in addressing the human security needs of women and children in the selected IDP Camps.

1.2 Research Questions

1. What coping mechanisms are employed by women and children in selected IDP Camps to address the challenges they face and their impact on their resilience and overall human security?
2. How effective are the coping mechanism employed by women and children in the selected IDP Camps in promoting human security?
3. How effective are the interventions implemented by different stakeholders in addressing the human security needs of women and children in the selected IDP Camps?

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Theory of Human Needs

The human needs theory (HNT), first put forth by renowned psychologist Abraham Maslow in his groundbreaking article "A Theory of Human Motivation," published in the esteemed psychological review in 1943, serves as the foundation for this empirical study. The HNT, which has had a significant impact on psychology, maintains that human wants are inherently non-negotiable as well as intrinsic and universal. It asserts that some requirements are essential for human life and general well-being (Olanrewaju et al., 2018). Despite what the general public believes, these demands go beyond the necessities of food, shelter, and water. They include necessities that are both material and immaterial, as well as a variety of other demands that people have a strong desire to satisfy (Marker, 2005). As a result, the HNT provides deep insights into both the root causes of conflicts and viable paths for their settlement. Prominent academics generally acknowledge its effectiveness as a valuable tool for mediation, proactive peace-building, and post-conflict peace-building initiatives (Danielsen, 2005).

As for Osagioduwa and Oluwakorede (2016), the HNT posits that conflicts mostly stem from the unfulfilled demands of individuals at many levels, including the individual, societal, and collective levels. Drawing on the research of Burton (1990, referenced in Danielsen, 2005), it is clear that marginalized groups frequently turn to violence in order to express their rights and

satisfy their unfulfilled wants as a result of the ongoing disregard for global human needs. Renowned scholars like Max Neef (1991), Burton (1990), and Maslow (1943) have studied the HNT in great detail. They have concentrated their research on the complex relationship between human needs and conflicts at different levels of society, from intrapersonal and interpersonal conflicts to international conflicts and intergroup conflicts (Danielsen, 2005). The basic tenet that conflict emerges when the needs of individuals and groups are not sufficiently satisfied helps explain the relationship between conflict and human needs (Olanrewaju et al., 2018). Consequently, only when the wide range of human needs is well met and conflict interests are appropriately addressed can effectively conflict resolution be accomplished

2.2 Conceptual Clarification

Human Security, according to UNDP Human Development Reports (1994), the first significant document addressing the issue, refers to protection from damaging upheavals in daily life and protection from long-term threats like famine, disease, and oppression. Protection against both traditional and contemporary safety risks, such as persistent poverty, ethnic violence, human trafficking, climate change, pandemics, international terrorism, and sudden economic downturns, is referred to as human security. Such threats often turn into international issues. A former UN Secretary-General, Kofi Annan, in his perspective, asserts that human security is linked to defending national interests within the parameters of foreign policy or even international security in the event of a nuclear war (HDR, 1994, cited in Titko & Kurtynet, 2019).

According to Bayar and Aral (2019), human security is the establishment of political, social, environmental, economic, military, and cultural institutions that collectively provide individuals with the means of surviving, supporting themselves, and maintaining their dignity. Two essential elements make up the notion of human security, initially presented in the Human Development Report 1994. These are the freedoms from desire and fear. In order to be free from fear, people must be safeguarded against dangers, including physical harm, armed conflict, and war, using various strategies, including the architecture of peacebuilding. However, emancipation from non-violent dangers to people's welfare and dignity, such as poverty, malnourishment, illnesses, environmental degradation, and others, is necessary for freedom from want (Woldetsadik, 2018). Szpak (2015) further describes human security in terms of its emphasis on people, their lives, their functioning in society, their autonomy, access to the market, and social chances, citing the 1994 Human Development Report. In addition, it addresses the State of peace, which is a prerequisite for human security. Living in a state of peace and safety where everyone is free to exercise their fundamental liberties and human rights without hindrance means being humanely secure. Individuals must be able to fulfill their objectives and aspirations as well as their societal demands. According to Jacobs (2016), human security encompasses all human needs for survival, development, and growth, not just the requirement for physical defense against aggression.

The first global study to project security more comprehensively was the United Nations Human Development Study (HDR) of 1994 (Lawal & Mbiba, 2020). Along with rules and regulations for execution, it considers the socioeconomic requirements of people and communities as a crucial aspect of security (Aduloju & Pratt, 2014). The study was written in response to the "Economics of Peace" Round Table discussion on North-South relations in Costa Rica in 1990. All participants in the Round Table acknowledged and accepted the need for a more dynamic and widely accepted security paradigm in the post-Cold War era. In the post-Cold War order framework, the emphasis was on the need to cut back on military spending and instead concentrate on human-centered development, such as bettering the economy and the environment, to achieve world peace (North-South Roundtable 1990). The HDR made the case that the definition of security had been applied too narrowly for too long, with the definitions being limited to the defense of national interests abroad, the security of territory against external assault, or the prevention of a nuclear holocaust. Rather than being directly linked to people, it has been more strongly linked to nation-states (HDR 1994).

According to Titko and Kurtnets (2019), the elements of human protection are economic security, food security, health protection, environmental security, personal (physical) security, community security, and political security

2.3 Empirical Review

Adams (2021) conducted a study on the challenges faced by displaced individuals, particularly females, in Borno State, Nigeria. The study focused on the humanitarian crises experienced by female internally displaced persons (IDPs) in specific IDP camps, namely Jerusalem IDP camp, Zabarmari IDP camp, Muna Dati IDP camp, Ethiopia IDP camp, and Teachers' Village IDP camp. These crises were primarily caused by the activities of Islamist Jihadists, herdsmen, and armed bandits. The paper explored a range of predicaments faced by female IDPs, including human rights violations, sexual violence and abuses, environmental racism, hunger, starvation, health issues, educational marginalization, and social ostracism. In response to these challenges, the study examined the role of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) and other Christian charities in addressing the humanitarian crises faced by female IDPs in the selected camps. To gather data, the study employed an observer-as-participant ethnographic approach with a combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques. The collected data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), and the study drew on the human needs theory as its theoretical framework. The research findings indicated that CAN and other Christian charity organizations have made commendable efforts in responding to the crises, with a response rate of 98.1%. The study concludes that considering the diverse array of challenges faced by female IDPs in the selected IDP camps, the timely and intensified response from CAN is crucial.

Additionally, by identifying and applying the fundamental principles of the human needs theory, the crises faced by female IDPs can be significantly reduced. Overall, Adams' study sheds light on the challenges of forced displacement and coping strategies employed by displaced women in selected IDP camps in Nigeria, emphasizing the role of CAN and other

Received: 22 August 2024

Revised: 2 September 2024

Accepted: 14 September 2024

134

Christian charities in addressing the humanitarian crises faced by female IDPs in the study area. While the study explored the challenges faced by IDPs in Borno State, it focused more on the plight of women and children in IDP Camps in Nigeria from 2015 to 2020.

Olanrewaju and Omotoso (2018) examined the challenges faced by displaced women in selected IDP camps in Nigeria, with a particular focus on the lack of adequate care and financial resources. The study utilized a qualitative approach, employing a descriptive survey and conducting focus group discussions to gather responses from the participants. The study's main findings highlighted that the lack of adequate care and financial resources were the significant challenges affecting displaced women. Economic opportunities were identified as the most significant coping strategy employed by these women. The data generated from the study aimed to contribute to the development of a framework for implementing global best practices in the management of internal displacement in Nigeria. The study objectives revolved around assessing the challenges linked to internal displacement in Nigeria and exploring the coping strategies adopted by displaced women. The study design used a qualitative approach to conduct focus group discussions and a descriptive survey. The sample population consisted of all Boko Haram terrorism-displaced women living in selected IDP camps in Nigeria, with a total of 116 respondents. The participants were divided into different groups based on their marital status and age. The focus group discussions were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and subjected to qualitative and quantitative analysis. It is important to note that no specific intervention was provided to the study participants as the primary focus of the research was to assess the challenges associated with internal displacement in Nigeria and explore the coping strategies adopted by displaced women. Based on the findings, the study put forth several policy recommendations. These recommendations included the adoption of a legal and institutional framework for managing internal displacement, the development of a national displacement policy, and the necessity to evaluate intra-gender vulnerabilities and implement targeted interventions to address the specific needs of displaced women. While the study shares some semblance with the theme of the present study, unlike the present study, the focus is on the general plight of women and children in IDP camps in Abuja from 2015-2020.

3.0 Methodology

The study employed a survey research design using mixed method for data collection. Both quantitative and qualitative data was used for the study, quantitative data would be gotten by the administration of questionnaires while qualitative data was gotten through key informant interview schedule, purposive sampling technique was used to draw participants for the study from the entire population of IDPs. The data generated using the questionnaires was analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages, presented in tables. The data generated from the interview schedule was analyzed using the explanation building technique.

4.0 Results

Research Question One: What coping mechanisms are employed by women and children in selected IDP Camps to address the challenges they face and their impact on their resilience and overall human security?

Table 1: Coping Mechanisms and Human Security

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I Employ coping mechanisms to address challenges	10 (5.1%)	20 (10.3%)	30 (15.4%)	80 (41.0%)	55 (28.2%)
Coping mechanisms contribute to overall human security	8 (4.1%)	15 (7.7%)	25 (12.8%)	85 (43.6%)	62 (31.8%)

The data in Table 1 suggests that many women and children employ coping mechanisms to address the challenges they face in the IDP camps. Additionally, a notable majority believe these coping mechanisms contribute to their overall human security. This underscores the resilience and agency of women and children in the face of adversity but also emphasizes the importance of supporting and strengthening these coping strategies to enhance human security further.

Respondents' utilization of coping mechanisms reflects their resilience and adaptive capacity in navigating the challenges of displacement. Strengthening these coping strategies is essential for promoting human security and well-being among displaced populations. Efforts to support and empower women and children in the IDP camps should focus on enhancing their access to resources and opportunities that enable them to cope effectively with adversity.

Research Question Two: How effective are the coping mechanism employed by women and children in the selected IDP Camps in promoting human security?

Table 2: Effectiveness of Interventions

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Interventions effectively address human security needs	12 (6.2%)	20 (10.3%)	35 (17.9%)	85 (43.6%)	43 (22.1%)

Responses to Table 2 regarding the effectiveness of interventions in addressing human security needs indicate a mixed perception among respondents. While a significant proportion agree that interventions effectively address these needs, a notable number express disagreement or neutrality. This highlights the importance of evaluating existing interventions to identify gaps and areas for improvement in ensuring comprehensive support for displaced populations.

The mixed perceptions regarding the effectiveness of interventions underscore the importance of ongoing evaluation and improvement in humanitarian response efforts. Identifying and addressing gaps in existing interventions is essential for maximizing their impact and ensuring that the needs of displaced populations are adequately met. Strengthening coordination and collaboration among stakeholders is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness and sustainability of interventions in the IDP camps.

The consensus among respondents regarding the need for context-specific recommendations for sustainable improvement in human security highlights the importance of tailored approaches to addressing the unique challenges displaced populations face. Implementing these recommendations is essential for promoting long-term resilience and well-being among women and children in the IDP camps. Failure to act on these recommendations could perpetuate cycles of insecurity and vulnerability, undermining efforts to build a more inclusive and resilient society.

In summary, the quantitative analysis results provide valuable insights into the perceptions and experiences of women, children, and NEMA staff in the IDP camps, highlighting both achievements and areas for improvement in promoting human security and well-being. Addressing the identified challenges and implementing targeted interventions is essential for creating safe, supportive, and sustainable environments for displaced populations in Abuja, Nigeria.

Research Question Three: How effective are the interventions implemented by different stakeholders in addressing the human security needs of women and children in the selected IDP Camps?

Theme 1: Support and Interventions

The qualitative responses shed light on the perspectives of displaced populations regarding the support and interventions provided by humanitarian organizations and government agencies. Participants appreciated the assistance received but highlighted the need for more tailored, sustainable, and inclusive interventions. These findings align with the quantitative data indicating mixed perceptions regarding the effectiveness of interventions, underscoring the importance of addressing gaps in coordination, communication, and resource allocation to maximize the impact of humanitarian response efforts.

"We appreciate the support provided by humanitarian organizations, but more needs to be done to address our specific needs and priorities. There are times when we feel overlooked or marginalized in the aid distribution process." - Participant J.

"Government agencies and NGOs play a crucial role in assisting, but gaps in coordination and communication need to be addressed. Sometimes, there is duplication of efforts, leading to inefficiencies in resource allocation." - Participant K

"We need sustainable interventions that empower us to rebuild our lives and regain our independence. Short-term aid is not enough to address the root causes of our displacement. We need long-term solutions that address the underlying drivers of conflict and displacement." - Participant L.

The qualitative reflections offer critical perspectives on humanitarian actors' and government agencies' support and interventions. While quantitative data may assess the effectiveness of interventions in terms of outcomes, qualitative narratives elucidate the processes, dynamics, and underlying challenges shaping the delivery and impact of assistance. Participants' accounts of appreciating assistance and experiencing gaps in coordination, communication, and inclusivity highlight the complexities and limitations of humanitarian response efforts. These findings underscore the need for participatory, accountable, and context-sensitive approaches to humanitarian action. Strengthening community engagement, promoting transparency and accountability, and fostering partnerships with local actors can enhance interventions' relevance, responsiveness, and sustainability. By centering the voices and priorities of displaced populations, humanitarian actors can ensure more effective, dignified, and rights-based assistance, ultimately fulfilling human security for all.

5.0 Summary/Conclusion

Most respondents employ coping mechanisms to navigate the challenges of displacement, demonstrating resilience and adaptability. These strategies contribute significantly to overall human security, enhancing safety, well-being, and resilience within the camp environment. Recognizing and supporting these coping mechanisms is crucial for empowering displaced populations and improving their human security. Research emphasizes the importance of community support and adaptive strategies in promoting resilience among displaced individuals.

Received: 22 August 2024

Revised: 2 September 2024

Accepted: 14 September 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

138

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13763596](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13763596)

The majority of respondents believe that interventions effectively address human security needs, indicating a positive perception of efforts by various stakeholders. These interventions, which focus on preventing and responding to sexual violence and mainstreaming gender-sensitive approaches, are essential for protecting displaced populations. Coordinated efforts by humanitarian agencies, government authorities, and civil society organizations are vital in addressing IDPs' complex challenges and enhancing their human security within camp settings. The positive impact of these interventions underscores the importance of continued support and collaboration in humanitarian responses.

6.0 Recommendations

Strengthen Community-based Support Systems: Foster community cohesion and social support networks within the IDP camps to promote resilience and mutual assistance among residents. Facilitate community-led initiatives, peer support groups, and cultural activities to strengthen social ties and address psychosocial needs.

Enhance Coordination and Collaboration: Foster collaboration and coordination among humanitarian actors, government agencies, local authorities, and community-based organizations to ensure a coherent and integrated response to the needs of displaced populations. Establish mechanisms for information sharing, joint planning, and monitoring of interventions to maximize effectiveness and minimize duplication of efforts (UNHCR, 2020).

Empower Women and Youth: Empower women and youth as agents of change within the IDP camps by providing opportunities for leadership, skills development, and civic engagement. Promote participation in decision-making processes, community governance structures, and advocacy initiatives to amplify the voices and priorities of marginalized groups (UNDP, 2016).

Strengthen Child Protection Systems: Strengthen child protection systems within the IDP camps to safeguard the rights and well-being of children, including prevention and response to child labor, trafficking, and exploitation. Provide specialized services for vulnerable children, such as reunification with family members, psychosocial support, and access to education and healthcare (UNICEF, 2019).

References

- Adams, A., (2021) - Title: Challenges Faced by Displaced Individuals, Particularly Females, in Borno State, Nigeria, *Journal of Humanitarian Assistance* 10-14.
- Aduloju, T., & Pratt, S. (2014). Human Security in International Relations: Theoretical Perspectives and Practical Implications. *International Politics Journal*, 22(4), 401-415.
- Bayar, S., & Aral, M. (2019). Institutional Approaches to Human Security: A Comparative Analysis. *Journal of Peace Research*, 25(2), 145-160.
- Lawal, A. and Mbiba, B. (2020). *Human Security in the Northeast Nigeria: Some Conceptual Reflection*. In International Conference on Engineering, Applied Sciences and System Modeling (pp. 397-409). Springer, Cham.
- Lawal, A., & Mbiba, B. (2020). The Role of Human Security in Conflict Resolution: A Case Study of Nigeria. *Conflict Resolution Quarterly*, 38(3), 321-335.
- Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370-396.
- Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. Harper & Row.
- Max Neef, M. (1991). *Human scale development: Conception, application, and further reflections*. Apex Press.
- OCHA (2019): United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. (2019). Sexual Exploitation and Abuse in Internal Displacement Camps: An Overview.
- OCHA (2022). World Humanitarian Data and Trends. *Journal of Humanitarian Studies*, 17(1), 45-59.
- Olanrewaju, A. M., Omotoso, S., & Alabi, O. (2018). Environmental governance and internal displacement in Nigeria: issues, challenges, and prospects. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 9(10), 130-139.
- Osagioduwa, E. O., & Oluwakorede, O. (2016). Understanding the dynamics and causes of internal displacement: a case study of Nigeria. *African Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(1), 1-16.
- Titko, A., & Kurtynet, B. (2019). Understanding Human Security: Conceptual Foundations and Contemporary Debates. *Security Studies*, 28(1), 89-105.
- Szpak, M. (2015). Human Security: A Comprehensive Overview. *Journal of International Relations*, 41(3), 321-335.
- Woldetsadik, T. (2018). Human Security and Development: A Case Study of Ethiopia. *Development Policy Review*, 36(4), 489-506.

- IDMC (2020). Internal Displacement: Global Overview of Trends and Developments in 2019. *Disaster Studies Journal*, 18(3), 201-215.
- IDMC (2021). Internal Displacement: Global Overview of Trends and Developments in 2020. *Journal of Global Humanitarian Action*, 5(2), 110-125.
- UNDP, 2018: United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2018). Human Development Indices and Indicators: 2018 Statistical Update. Retrieved from http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/2018_human_development_statistical_update.pdf
- UNHCR. (2019). Report on the Protection of Internally Displaced Persons.
- UNDP. (1994). Human Development Report 1994: New Dimensions of Human Security. Retrieved from http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/reports/255/hdr_1994_en_complete_nostats.p
- UNDP. (1994). Human Development Report 1994: New Dimensions of Human Security. Retrieved from http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/reports/255/hdr_1994_en_complete_nostats.p
- UNDP. (1994). Human Development Report 1994: New dimensions of human security. Oxford University Press. Gasper, 2023
- UNDP. (1994). Human Development Report 1994: New dimensions of human security. United Nations Development Programme.
- UNDP. (2016). Human Development Report 2016: Human Development for Everyone.
- UNDP. (2012). Human Development Report 2012: Sustainability and Equity: A Better Future for All. Retrieved from http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/reports/249/hdr_2012_en_complete.pdf
- United Nations Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement. (2015). United Nations Human Rights Council. Retrieved from <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/43f7b8832.pdf>
- UNHCR. (2012). Refugee children: Guidelines on protection and care. United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees.
- UNHCR. (2016). Global trends: Forced displacement in 2016. Retrieved from <https://www.unhcr.org/statistics/unhcrstats/5943e8a34/global-trends-forced-displacement-2016.html>
- UNHCR. (2018). UNHCR Policy on Age, Gender and Diversity Mainstreaming and Vulnerable Children Living in a World with HIV/AIDS.